
C*-algebraic Popoviciu Conjecture

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Abstract: We formulate C*-algebraic version of Popoviciu Conjecture (Rahman-Sudbery Theorem) and show that it holds for degree 2 polynomials over commutative unital C*-algebras.

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Let $\mathbb{C}[z]$ be the set of all polynomials over \mathbb{C} . Conjecture of Popoviciu [2] which is later proved partially by Rahman [1] and fully by Sudbery [3] states the following.

Theorem 0.1. [1-3] (*Popoviciu Conjecture/Rahman-Sudbery Theorem*) Let $n \geq 2$ and $p(z) = (z - a_1)(z - a_2) \cdots (z - a_n) \in \mathbb{C}[z]$ be such that $a_j \neq a_k$ for some $1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k$. Then the polynomial

$$q(z) := p(z)p'(z) \cdots p^{(n-1)}(z) \in \mathbb{C}[z]$$

has at least $n + 1$ distinct zeros.

In this note, we formulate C*-algebraic analogue of Theorem 0.1 and verify it for degree 2 polynomials over commutative unital C*-algebras.

Conjecture 0.2. (*C*-algebraic Popoviciu Conjecture*) Let \mathcal{A} be a unital commutative C*-algebra. Let $n \geq 2$ and $p(z) = (z - a_1)(z - a_2) \cdots (z - a_n) \in \mathcal{A}[z]$ be such that $a_j \neq a_k$ for some $1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k$. Then the polynomial

$$q(z) := p(z)p'(z) \cdots p^{(n-1)}(z) \in \mathcal{A}[z]$$

has at least $n + 1$ distinct zeros.

Theorem 0.3. Conjecture 0.2 holds for degree 2 polynomials.

Proof. Let \mathcal{A} be a unital commutative C*-algebra. Let

$$p(z) = (z - a)(z - b) \in \mathcal{A}[z]$$

with $a \neq b$. Then

$$q(z) = p(z)p'(z) = (z - a)(z - b)(2z - (a + b)).$$

Hence

$$p(a) = p(b) = p\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = 0.$$

Note that

$$a \neq b, \quad a \neq \frac{a+b}{2}, \quad b \neq \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

□

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